

PSYCHOLOGICAL INFLUENCE OF MASS CULTURE ON THE FORMATION OF SPIRITUAL VALUES OF ADOLESCENTS

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Abstract. This article describes the psychological impact of mass culture on the formation of students' moral values, the psychological impact and its main goals, the types of psychological impact and the scientific views of psychologists on how it is implemented. written about.

Key words: Adolescents, mass culture, spiritual value, psychological influence, media, value types, transition period.

Introduction. One of the urgent tasks facing the educational process today is the use of national values and traditions in the education of a well-rounded person. At the same time, in our country, raising a mentally mature and mature person to adulthood has been raised to the level of state policy. After all, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev "On measures to further improve the project management system in the field of information and communication technologies" dated August 29, 2017 No. PQ-3245 [1] and information and public using modern technologies security, as well as strengthening measures aimed at ensuring law and order, adoption of decisions on the development of proposals for the improvement of the normative legal framework in the field of ensuring the information security of the State information systems and resources, as well as the national segment of the Internet, preventing dependence on information sources in our country and information serves to ensure safety.

In our country, a lot of attention is paid to the issues of raising a mature generation, and the issue of teenagers and their education has been raised to the level of priority in the life of the society. In particular, it includes priorities such as fundamental reform of the organizational and legal mechanisms for ensuring a healthy and stable socio-spiritual environment and peace, harmony and tranquility in the society and family arising from our national and spiritual values, because ; The President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev visited the Youth Forum of Uzbekistan on December 25, 2020 and stated the following at the meeting:

"No matter how difficult it is, we must find unique and effective methods of youth education that are in tune with today. We need to protect our dear children from destructive and harmful ideas, crime, drug addiction, indifference, spiritual poverty" in order to educate the generation on the basis of their national values, traditions and customs, they must have the right to determine their own destiny, i.e. independence.

In order to educate young people in the spirit of patriotism, respect for our national traditions and values, to bring up a spiritually mature and physically healthy generation, to protect their rights and interests, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 12, 2019 "Psychological and pedagogical support of students" - Decision No. 577 on

further improvement of support works; ORQ-637 of September 23, 2020 "Law on Education" of the Republic of Uzbekistan; Resolution No. 23¹ of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 18, 2021 "On approval of the concept of development of state policy regarding youth in Uzbekistan until 2025"; Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 "2022 It should also be recognized that the Decree No. PF-60 "On the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2026" was adopted.

First of all, it is appropriate to dwell on the effect. Influence is the process and result of an individual changing the behavior, skills, goals, imagination and evaluation of another person (the object of influence) through cooperation with him. Psychological influence is influencing another person's state, thoughts, feelings and actions with the help of psychological means, giving him the right and time to respond to this influence. Resistance to alien influence is resistance to the influence of another person using psychological means. The initiator of influence is the one who first makes an effort to influence. The addressee of influence is the person to whom the first influence action is directed. In subsequent interactions, the initiative may pass from one subject to another, but the one who initiates the interaction is called the initiator, and the one who first feels its influence is called the addressee. However, in the process of interpersonal communication, the interaction of subjects becomes regular, therefore, in many cases, the subject can be both the initiator and the addressee of influence at the same time.

Open psychological cooperation is an interaction in which goals are not disclosed or hidden in advance. Covert psychological cooperation is an interaction in which goals are not announced or hidden under the guise of overt cooperation. The tools of complete psychological influence include verbal, paralinguistic and non-verbal tools. Verbal signals are words, first of all, their meaning, at the same time, the character of the words used, the choice of expression, the correctness of the speech or the types of errors in it. Paralinguistic signals are the peculiarities of speech, pronunciation of individual words and sounds. Non-verbal signals - mutual location of subjects in space, poses, gestures, eye contact, appearance, touches, smells.

Psychological influence is carried out for three purposes:

1. Satisfying one's needs with the help of others or through them;
2. To confirm the fact of its existence and the importance of this fact;
3. To overcome the space-time limit of one's existence.

In fact, the first of these goals includes the other two goals, if we consider the desire to assert one's existence and overcome the space-time limit as needs. However, the difference between the three goals is quite significant. In the first case, psychological influence is used to satisfy other needs, not the need for influence. In the second case, the influence serves as a sign, indicator, proof of the fact of the influencer's existence and the importance of this existence. In the third case, the effect itself is considered a need and appears as a manifestation of the aspirations of all beings - overcoming the space-time limit of their existence.

Destructive processes in the spiritual life of modern society threaten the vitality of the entire state. This phenomenon serves as a catalyst for the change of individual and public

morality expressed in the growth of immorality and legal nihilism. To combat this phenomenon, it is necessary to create and implement a matrix of moral values.

Despite the individual nature of spiritual values, their uniqueness and individuality, there are values of a universal order that are available to many at the same time and cover several areas of a given human activity. These include kindness, honesty, good upbringing, hard work, humanity, tolerance, decency. And when these kinds of values cease to be important at a certain historical period, the intervention of the state or public organizations becomes necessary - integral components of a developed civil society and democracy.

Taking into account the current state of society, which can be characterized as a period of transition, it is important to analyze the moral values of young people, their relationship with the surrounding reality, and predict their future state based on the obtained data.

Mass media imposes a combination of thoughts, feelings and situations, which especially affects young people, that is, there is a flattening of the personality, there is a process of manipulation aimed at expanding and creating artificial needs: the human desire for pleasure and should avoid unpleasant things. But a person who has become a slave to consumption is not able to think, reason and act independently. In hedonistically understood life, instincts dominate and lose their true meaning. The idea of a paradise on earth, based on money and material goods, filled only with pleasant and joyful emotions, is certainly not true, and in fact, a person often leads himself astray. it hardens. the ability to be happy.

Another type of value typification is related to the satisfaction of human needs: vital needs related to the preservation and continuation of life (well-being, comfort, safety, health); interactionist - communication and interaction with other people; socialization - learning norms, patterns and standards of behavior in society; Meaningful - needs that are fulfilled in achieving the meaning of life.

In adolescence, all boys and girls, without exception, have a tendency to anger, depression and hypochondria (depression - mental depression, hypochondria - panic), high impressionability, stuttering, increased feeling of personal inadequacy, high irritability, suspiciousness, fearlessness, constant doubt and judgment, tendency to self-analysis, tendency to ritual actions and obsession, separation from others, isolation, introversion, lack of empathy, tendency to be easily influenced by others, always looking for new impressions, circles, easy contact with a superficial character, excessive dependence and submission to the opinions of others, criticality and lack of initiative are manifested. Forces that are well aware of these laws of mental development of young people are pulling them into the whirlpool of various religious, extremist, and terrorist ideas with methods of influence under the guise of mass culture.

Currently, mass media alone is enough to subjugate a country or people. The methods of using force, coercion, and influence through violence are being replaced by the technologies of convincing people of an idea and mind control. It is also difficult to blame those who use persuasion, because it is not easy to know what interests are hidden behind the ideas they promote. In this case, it becomes unclear who the conqueror is, and the population does not even understand who is fighting to conquer them. Since this struggle is carried out secretly, it cannot be resisted in an organized manner, and this factor determines the success of such aggressions.

Under the influence of popular culture, people develop bad taste and irresponsibility. The operation of the "yellow press" under the guise of democracy, which reflects the comic,

intimate realities, photos, various murders, and romantic conflicts of famous people, which is published in the society that has received the status of "entertainment industry", ensures the wider rooting of popular culture.

"Fake culture" causes tragedies such as self-limitation of a person. The number of people who sit for hours in front of the TV, computer or radio and watch the sunrise and sunset every day is increasing.

The principles and activities implemented in the field of spirituality in our republic served as the main method to prevent such negative situations that may arise in the society.

It is known that any sudden change in the system of dynamic stereotypes-reinforced behavior in a person causes a great psychological discomfort, in some cases, if such a situation lasts for a long time, it causes a shift in the psyche, neurotic states. The step-by-step transition to the market economy, the gradual tightening of economic factors in a mild form, without causing discomfort, actually served to prevent such discomfort and maintain mental balance among the members of the society.

It should be recognized that the exchange of spiritual values between different cultures, the mutual assimilation of the achievements of science, technology, is a regular process, and this process is a driving force for development. However, each nation has elements of culture that cover different spheres of life activity at different periods of its development, and cultural achievements are the product of the development of the social consciousness of each nation over hundreds of years. The simple appropriation of the culture and lifestyle of one nation by another nation causes tensions and tensions in the psychology and social consciousness of the nation, resulting in moral tensions in the society, moral differences between representatives of different generations. incorrect formation of spiritual values and spiritual conflicts arise.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it should be noted that in today's era, which is called the age of information, the age of potential, the age of electronics and information technologies, the qualities of awareness, sensitivity, vigilance are becoming a requirement of the times. That is, it is necessary to inculcate the duty and responsibility of awareness, sensitivity, and vigilance in the child's mind and heart, as well as to form primary ideas and concepts that awaken awareness, sensitivity, and vigilance during conversations.

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